

domized block design with four replications. One-half N and all P and K were applied before transplanting rice or sowing wheat. The remaining N was top-dressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk of crop growth. Because of acute Zn deficiency, 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha was applied to both crops. N, P, and K sources were urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. Recommended agronomic

practices were followed, and yield data were separately recorded. Samples were collected from the 0-15 cm soil layer after the 1982 wheat harvest, ground to pass through a 2-mm sieve, and analyzed for available P and K.

N application significantly improved rice and wheat grain yields (Table 1). The increase was 2.7 to 4.2 t/ha for rice and 1.8 to 3.7 t/ha for wheat. Applying P did

not increase yield of either crop earlier in the experiment because soil had high available P. After 1978, however, rice responded because soil P had declined in the N-alone treatment (Table 2). K application did not affect yield of either crop, indicating that continuous cropping of rice and wheat for 8 yr had not substantially depleted available K (Table 2). □

Table 1. Grain yield of rice and wheat in a long-term fertilizer experiment at Karnal, India. **Table 2. Available P and K status of sodic soil after a continuous 8-yr rice - wheat sequence, Karnal, India.**

Fertilizer treatments ^a	Yield (t/ha)							
	Rice			Wheat				
	Rice	Wheat	1974	1981	Av of 8 yr	1974-75	1981-82	Av of 8 yr
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	3.8	3.4	3.4	0.8	2.4	1.2	
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀	6.6	6.4	7.0	4.1	5.4	4.2	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	6.6	7.6	7.5	3.7	5.6	4.1	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀	6.6	7.7	7.4	4.1	5.6	4.2	
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	7.2	7.5	7.5	3.9	5.7	4.2	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	7.1	7.1	7.3	4.1	5.9	4.2	
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀	6.4	7.7	7.4	4.0	5.6	4.2	
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	6.8	6.8	7.1	4.1	5.6	4.2	
CD at 5%		.10	.09	.05	.08	.03	.03	

^aNumbers refer to kg N, P, and K/ha. Dose of fertilizer N was raised from 100 to 120 kg/ha from the 1978 rice crop.

Treatment		Available P	Available K
Rice	Wheat	(ppm)	(ppm)
Initial value 1974		15.0	160.0
after wheat 1981-82			
N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	N ₀ P ₀ K ₀	12.0	153.7
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀	5.7	152.5
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	18.0	156.2
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	N ₁₀₀	13.5	157.5
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂	10.3	152.5
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	18.5	183.7
N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	N ₁₀₀	10.7	173.7
N ₁₀₀	N ₁₀₀ P ₂₂ K ₄₂	11.5	175.0
CD at 5%		3.3	15.2

Applying basic slag to increase yield of a rice — wheat rotation

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In 1981-1982 we evaluated the effect of applying basic slag and P fertilizer on rice and wheat planted in acid laterite soils of Purulia, West Bengal. The physicochemical characteristics of the soils in the experimental farmer fields are in Table 1.

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of acid laterite soils in Purulia, West Bengal.

Site	Texture	pH	Organic carbon (%)	Total soluble salts (mmho/cm)	Av P (kg/ha)	Av K (kg/ha)
I	Loamy sand	4.80	0.32	0.14	6.39	108.98
II	Loamy sand	4.70	0.20	0.06	5.40	99.62
III	Sandy loam	5.20	0.72	0.19	7.73	122.47

Basic slag (100 mesh) containing 32.80% CaO and 1.61% P (2% citric acid soluble) was applied in 3 treatments: control; no basic slag; 1.25 to 2.50 t basic slag/ha, based on soil texture; and equal parts basic slag and well-rotted farmyard manure (FYM). Treatments were in 3 replications with 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha for rice IET2233 and wheat UP262. Sites I and II received 1.25 t basic slag/ha and site III received 2.50 t/ha. The mean pooled data for 1981-82 are in Table 2.

Basic slag alone and mixed with FYM increased rice yield 19.4 and 39.4%. The

residual effects of the amendments increased wheat yield 24.0 and 31.6%. Yield always increased more with basic slag and FYM, but results were statistically significant only at sites I and II for rice and only at site I for wheat. □

Table 2. Influence of basic slag on the yield of paddy and wheat in double crop sequences at Purulia, West Bengal.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Site I	Site II	Site III	Mean
<i>Rice</i>				
Control	2.7	2.6	3.2	2.8
1.25 or 2.50 t basic slag	3.0	2.9	4.1	3.4
Basic slag + FYM	3.9	3.8	4.1	3.9
CD at 5%	0.6	0.4	0.3	
<i>Wheat</i>				
Control	1.9	1.9	2.2	2.0
1.25 or 2.50 t basic slag	2.1	1.9	3.4	2.5
Basic slag + FYM	2.6	2.2	3.2	2.6
CD at 5%	0.4	0.5	0.9	